

How to Cite (APA): Üre, T., et al. (2025). Detection of cyber attacks with machine learning algorithms. In Proceedings of the IMSS'25 (pp. 226–239). Düzce University - Türkiye, 25–27 September 2025.

Detection of Cyber Attacks with Machine Learning Algorithms

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KEYWORDS - Cyber security, Machine learning, Cyber attack, Intrusion detection, Decision trees

ABSTRACT

Cyber-attack types and application areas have diversified considerably in the present era. The diversification of cyberattacks has led to a continuous increase in their effects. Consequently, detecting cyberattacks has become a crucial aspect of cybersecurity. Attacks such as Brute Force, HTTP DDoS, ICMP Flood, Port Scan, and Web Crawling have gained significant prominence in the cyber domain. The use of diverse techniques and methods has led to challenges in detecting these attack types, which, in turn, have undermined the comprehensive security of cyber systems. This study utilized the MSCAD data set, a frequently used dataset in intrusion detection systems, sourced from the Kaggle platform. Initially, the data set underwent a series of preprocessing steps, including data cleaning, removing low-variance features, and eliminating missing values. Subsequently, the pre-processed data set was analyzed using machine learning algorithms, including Random Forest, Decision Tree, Neural Network, Support Vector Machine (SVM), and K-Nearest Neighbours (KNN). Furthermore, the chi-square feature selection algorithm was applied to the pre-processed dataset, minimizing the number of features. Subsequently, the same machine learning algorithms were applied to the dataset and analyzed. This study conducted experiments on Orange3 and JupyterLab, and the results were compared. With the successful results obtained through machine learning algorithms, improvements can be made to Intrusion Detection Systems

1 INTRODUCTION

In today's technological age, the use of the internet and the number of internet-connected devices are continuously increasing. As our reliance on technological devices grows, so do the threats, attacks, and vulnerabilities associated with increased internet usage. Looking back, we observe that the educational and training levels of cyber attackers have significantly declined, yet the complexity, diversity, and intensity of attacks have risen. Consequently, ensuring security in this digital realm has become essential.

Today's prevalent types of cyberattacks are Brute Force, HTTP DDoS, ICMP Flood, Port Scanning, and Web Crawling, which malicious actors frequently exploit. Brute Force attacks attempt to access an account by trying all possible password combinations. HTTP DDoS (HTTP Distributed Denial of Service) attacks aim to turn off the normal operations of a web server by sending an overwhelming number of requests, often through bot networks, which overload the target server and hinder service for legitimate users. On the other hand, the ICMP Flood attack inundates the network with Internet Control Message Protocol (ICMP) packets, where attackers generate excessive ICMP traffic to prevent the network from responding. In a Port Scan attack, a sequence of requests is made to check specific access points on a network, allowing attackers to identify vulnerable or accessible services. Web Crawling is the automated scanning or indexing of a website's content by bots, often used by search engines and indexing services. Still, malicious entities can also exploit it to index and extract data from websites. Another feature in our dataset is the "Normal" category, which denotes regular network traffic, contrasting with other categories that signify abnormal or attack-driven behaviors.

Within cybersecurity, various datasets are available for attack detection. This study utilizes the MSCAD dataset from Kaggle, a dataset frequently used in Intrusion Detection Systems. We examine the performance of machine learning classification models alongside a chi-square feature selection algorithm for attack detection. Initially, data preprocessing steps were conducted, including data cleaning, removal of low-variance features, and handling of missing values. Initially comprising 67 features and 128,799 rows, the dataset was refined to 57 features and 92,035 rows. Subsequently, machine learning algorithms such as Random Forest, Decision Tree, Neural Network, Support Vector Machine (SVM), and K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) were applied to the preprocessed dataset. The chi-square feature selection algorithm was implemented to minimize the number of features. Machine learning algorithms were then reapplied, and the analysis was conducted on the updated dataset. This research was carried out using Orange3 and JupyterLab, where a comparative analysis of the results demonstrated the efficacy of the machine learning models.

The novelty of this study lies in its focus on optimizing traditional machine learning algorithms using chi-square feature selection on the MSCAD dataset, which has not been widely explored in recent literature. Unlike previous works that primarily use benchmark datasets such as NSL-KDD or CICIDS2017, this study focuses on real-world attack types, employing detailed preprocessing to enhance accuracy and efficiency. The research addresses a critical gap in reproducibility and feature engineering methods in cyber attack detection studies by providing a transparent, end-to-end machine learning pipeline.

The second section of the article reviews previous studies on this subject. The third section provides an overview of the dataset and the types of attacks it contains, followed by an introduction to machine learning and cybersecurity. The fourth section delivers a comprehensive explanation of the methodology. The final section discusses the experiments, analysis results, and performance evaluations for attack detection and analysis.

2 LITERATURE

A literature review reveals numerous studies utilizing machine learning or deep learning techniques to detect cyberattacks in datasets containing various types of attacks. Upon examining these studies in detail, particularly those published in recent years, specific attention has been given to the types of machine learning techniques used, the types of cyberattacks addressed, whether feature selection methods were employed, and the evaluation metrics used. Ling et al. (2023) review state-of-the-art adversarial attacks on Windows Portable Executable (PE) malware detection, highlighting challenges in preserving malware format, executability, and maliciousness. They categorize attack methods and defenses, emphasizing problem-space strategies for creating adversarial PE malware and concluding with opportunities for future research to enhance detection robustness [1]. K Safi Ullah et al. (2023) propose a Transformer Neural Network-based intrusion detection system (TNN-IDS) for MQTT-enabled IoT networks. Leveraging the MQTT-IoT-IDS2020 dataset, TNN-IDS achieves over 99.9% accuracy, surpassing existing ML and DL methods. Its architecture handles imbalanced data and complex relationships, offering scalable and efficient detection of malicious activities [2]. On the other hand, Calp and Bütüner focused on detecting cyberattacks targeting IoT-based network devices using machine learning algorithms. In their study, data preprocessing was performed, followed by the application of algorithms including Artificial Neural Network (ANN), Random Forest (RF), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Naive Bayes (NB), and Logistic Regression (LR). Random Forest achieved the highest performance in detecting cyberattacks, with an accuracy of 99.6% [3].

Amal K. Alkhalifa et al. (2025) propose a Hybrid Dung Beetle Optimization-based Dimensionality Reduction with Deep Learning Cybersecurity Solution (HDBODR-DLCS) for IoT networks. Combining Z-score normalization, feature selection, bidirectional recurrent neural networks, and hyperparameter tuning, the method achieves superior intrusion detection with 99.33% accuracy, 87.07% sensitivity, and 98.31% specificity. It outperforms existing models in accuracy and computational efficiency [4]. Amal K. Alkhalifa et al. (2025) present a Hybrid Dung Beetle Optimization-based Dimensionality Reduction with a Deep Learning-based Cybersecurity Solution (HDBODR-DLCS) for Internet of Things (IoT) networks. The proposed method integrates Z-score normalization for data preprocessing, a hybrid dung beetle optimization algorithm for feature selection, an attention bidirectional recurrent neural network (ABiRNN) for intrusion detection, and artificial rabbits optimization (ARO) for hyperparameter tuning. Evaluated on a benchmark intrusion detection dataset, the HDBODR-DLCS achieved superior performance with an accuracy of 99.33%, a sensitivity of 87.07%, a specificity of 98.31%, and an F1-score of 87.85%, outperforming existing models in both accuracy and computational efficiency [5]. Osman et al. (2024) propose ELG-IDS, an ensemble learning framework incorporating genetic feature selection for detecting RPL attacks in IoT networks. The system effectively identifies version number, decreased rank, and DIS flooding attacks with 99.18%, 99.38%, and 99.66% accuracy, respectively. Utilizing a comprehensive dataset and stacking-based meta-learning, ELG-IDS surpasses existing solutions by achieving an overall accuracy of 97.9%, demonstrating improved precision, recall, and F-score. This framework significantly enhances IoT security by providing robust and scalable intrusion detection optimized for computational efficiency and high detection rates, advancing the protection of RPL-based IoT networks against internal threats [6].

Bindu Bala and Sunny Behal (2024) review AI techniques for detecting IoT-based DDoS attacks, addressing machine learning and deep learning methods from 2019 to 2023. The study highlights a comparative analysis of datasets, AI software, and classification methods. Notable

findings include 99.9% accuracy using kNN models and advanced insights into the botnet lifecycle. The paper identifies research gaps, emphasizes the need for robust detection frameworks, and presents AI-based solutions as superior for scalable IoT DDoS mitigation [7]. Fu et al. (2025) introduce TSIDS, a spatiotemporal fusion gating Multilayer Perceptron (gMLP) for network intrusion detection. TSIDS integrates temporal correlations using BiLSTM and spatial relationships via customized gMLP, enhancing detection accuracy. Accuracy was achieved by up to 99.9% on four datasets, and F1 scores improved over benchmarks. Results confirm TSIDS's superior performance in detecting anomalies and its generalizability across various network scenarios, demonstrating a robust solution for modern intrusion challenges in dynamic and heterogeneous IoT environments [8]. Kumari and Mishra (2024) propose Tachyon, a stacked ensemble intrusion detection framework enhanced with Bayesian optimization. It integrates diverse machine learning models, including Random Forest, Decision Tree, and XGBoost, along with advanced sampling techniques such as SMOTE and ADASYN. Tested on the IoTID20 dataset, Tachyon achieved 99.8% accuracy, a 3.6% improvement, and an AUC of 1. The framework demonstrates robust attack detection and efficient performance, addressing class imbalance and optimizing dimensionality reduction. This makes Tachyon a scalable and effective cybersecurity solution for IoT networks [9]. Pardeshi and Patil (2024) present an efficient intrusion detection system using shallow machine learning models on the NSL-KDD dataset. The system incorporates feature selection via SelectKBest and Correlation Feature Selection, with optimal hyperparameters determined through Grid Search. Gradient Boost achieved 99.88% accuracy in binary classification, while Gradient Boost and Random Forest reached 90% accuracy in multiclass classification. These results demonstrate improved detection rates and efficiency compared to existing models, providing a robust solution for intrusion detection in cybersecurity [10].

Noor Ullah Bacha et al. (2024) introduce a hybrid ensemble machine learning framework for detecting Cross-Site Scripting (XSS) attacks. Utilizing Logistic Regression, SVM, XGBoost, CatBoost, and DNN models, their system achieved a 99.87% detection accuracy on the XSS-Attacks-2021 dataset. With low false positives (0.13%) and false negatives (0.19%), the approach proves scalable and adaptable for real-time applications, effectively addressing XSS attack challenges in evolving web environments [11]. Xiao et al. (2025) propose GRAIN, a novel framework that combines Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) and reinforcement learning for reconstructing multi-step attacks. GRAIN eliminates alert redundancies, uncovers causal relationships, and reconstructs attack scenarios with enhanced accuracy. Tested on four datasets, GRAIN achieved a 94.68% reduction ratio and demonstrated higher precision, recall, and completeness than traditional methods. This framework effectively identifies attack paths, addresses expertise dependence, and ensures efficient, context-aware intrusion detection in complex security environments[12].

Shafee et al. (2025) evaluate LLM-based chatbots, such as GPT-4, GPT4all, and Dolly, for Cyber Threat Intelligence (CTI) tasks using Open-Source Intelligence (OSINT). In binary classification, GPT-4 achieved an F1 score of 0.94, while GPT4all scored 0.90. All chatbots underperformed for Named Entity Recognition (NER), highlighting limitations in cybersecurity-specific contexts. The study demonstrates the potential of chatbots in processing OSINT, but stresses the need for improvements in NER capabilities to replace specialized models [13] effectively. Vanlalruata Hnamte and Jamal Hussain (2023) propose a dependable Intrusion Detection System (IDS) using a Deep Convolutional Neural Network (DCNN) framework. Evaluated on the ISCX2012, Kaggle DDoS, CICIDS2017, and CICIDS2018 datasets, the model achieved accuracy levels of 99.79% to 100%, outperforming traditional DNNs. It demonstrates robust detection capabilities, low false positive rates, and efficient training and inference times. The study highlights DCNN's ability

to adapt to evolving threats and handle real-time network traffic effectively, positioning it as a superior solution for intrusion detection in dynamic network environments[13]. Hamza Alkofahi et al. (2024) analyze security vulnerabilities in additive manufacturing systems, specifically Stratasys Dimension Elite 3D printers. They demonstrate Man-in-the-Middle (MitM) attacks, including model sniffing, replacement, and sabotage, exploiting non-encrypted communication protocols. The model's sabotaging attack resulted in significant structural changes while maintaining its external appearance. Their methodology achieved minimal detection overhead (0.015 seconds). This research highlights the urgent need for robust encryption and security mechanisms to protect intellectual property and ensure the reliability of additive manufacturing systems[14]. Reddy Sai Sindhu Theja and Gopal K. Shyam (2021) propose a hybrid intrusion detection system combining the Oppositional Crow Search Algorithm (OCSA) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN) to detect Denial-of-Service (DoS) attacks in cloud computing. Evaluated using the KDD Cup 99 dataset, their method achieved 98.18% precision, 95.13% recall, 93.56% F-measure, and 94.12% accuracy. The approach outperformed traditional methods by optimizing feature selection and classification processes, ensuring robust and efficient intrusion detection in cloud environments [15]. Ibrahim Hayatu Hassan et al. (2024) provide a comprehensive review of the Honey Badger Algorithm (HBA), highlighting its growth, applications, and enhancements since its inception. With 52 studies presenting improved variants using chaotic maps and multi-objective mechanisms and 20 hybrids combining HBA with other algorithms, the paper emphasizes its efficiency, rapid convergence, and applicability across optimization problems. The survey highlights HBA's superiority in tackling NP-hard problems compared to traditional algorithms, such as PSO and CMA-ES, making it a versatile and robust optimization tool across diverse domains [16]. However, this study differs in that it employs chi-square selection and evaluates performance across both Orange3 and JupyterLab environments, offering a broader assessment perspective.

3 TESTBED & USED TECHNOLOGIES

All experiments were conducted using JupyterLab (v3.6.3), Orange3 (v3.35), Python (v3.10.9), and Scikit-learn (v1.2.2). The system configuration included an Intel Core i7-1165G7 processor, 16 GB of RAM, and the Windows 11 operating system. For this research, the following methods and attacks are employed, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Flow Diagram

3.1 Machine Learning

If this template is used when writing the full paper, headers and footers will be set automatically. Authors are only asked to replace the "SX-YY" number with the paper code that has been assigned when the abstract was accepted) on the header of the first page and on the footer of other pages in order to set a unique page number in the Proceedings.

Machine learning has empowered computers to learn in ways analogous to human learning. As a critical field within artificial intelligence, machine learning focuses on developing algorithms and models that enable computers to interpret and generalize from data without being explicitly programmed for each task. By utilizing structured data inputs and applying sophisticated learning mechanisms, machine learning algorithms can identify complex patterns, make predictions, and enhance decision-making processes across various domains, including cybersecurity, finance, healthcare, and beyond.

3.1.1 Types of Machine Learning

This study employs several widely recognized machine learning techniques, each well-suited to handling large datasets and generating accurate predictions. The types of machine learning applied include K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Neural Networks, Decision Trees, Random Forests, and Support Vector Machine (SVM). These algorithms are selected due to their robust application in data analysis and predictive modeling, providing a basis for exploring data relationships and effectively identifying patterns. Each method contributes unique strengths in managing classification tasks, regression analysis, and clustering, which are essential in machine learning applications.

3.1.1.1 K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN)

K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) is a non-parametric, instance-based learning algorithm widely used in machine learning and data mining. KNN operates by determining the class or value of a data point based on the data points closest to it in the feature space, often identified through Euclidean distance. The "K" in KNN refers to the number of nearest neighbors considered for classification or prediction. For example, if $K = 3$, the algorithm examines the three closest points to determine the target point's category or value. This algorithm is particularly beneficial for classification tasks involving discrete categories and is known for its simplicity, versatility, and intuitive approach. However, KNN can be computationally intensive on large datasets, as the algorithm must calculate distances to each neighboring data point. Despite this, KNN remains a powerful technique for tasks where interpretability and simplicity are prioritized [17].

3.1.1.2 Neural Network

Neural Networks are foundational models in machine learning and deep learning that emulate the workings of the human brain. They consist of interconnected artificial neurons arranged in layers, which collectively learn to identify complex relationships within data. Neural networks are typically structured with an input, one or more hidden layers, and an output layer. Each neuron in a layer is connected to neurons in the subsequent layer, with weights assigned to these connections that adjust as the model learns, effectively 'tuning' the network. Through backpropagation, neural networks minimize errors between predicted and actual outputs, refining the model's accuracy. Neural networks excel in pattern recognition, image and speech processing, and solving complex problems. They are highly adaptive, making them suitable for scenarios where data exhibits non-linear relationships. However, neural networks often require substantial computational resources and large datasets for practical training, especially when employing deep learning models with numerous hidden layers[18].

3.1.1.3 Decision Tree

The Decision Tree classifier is a widely adopted machine learning model used primarily for classification, but it can also be applied to regression tasks. Decision Trees partition the data into subsets based on specific features, forming a tree-like structure. A decision rule is applied at each "node" of the tree, dividing the dataset into branches based on criteria like the Gini coefficient, information gain, or entropy. This process is recursive until the data reaches the "leaves," where classification decisions are made. Decision Trees are advantageous for their interpretability, as they allow for transparent decision-making, with each path in the tree traceable back to a specific set of features. Despite this, Decision Trees can be prone to overfitting on training data, mainly when the tree grows too complex. To counter this, techniques like pruning, which involve cutting branches that add little value, are often used to improve the model's generalization. Decision Trees are preferred in situations requiring model transparency and ease of implementation [5].

3.1.1.4 Random Forest

The Random Forest technique is a highly effective method for handling binary and multiclass classification problems, and it is known for achieving strong performance with a relatively small number of parameters. By constructing multiple decision trees, Random Forest provides more robust predictions than individual trees, as it reduces the likelihood of overfitting and improves generalization across data samples.

In a Random Forest, each decision tree branches out from a root node, creating nodes and branches until a stopping criterion is met. This branching process continues as each tree attempts to make an optimal decision by splitting the dataset into subsets based on specific feature values. Ultimately, predictions are made by averaging or voting on the outputs from all trees, resulting in a

collective decision that balances the diversity of individual trees. This ensemble approach enables Random Forest models to achieve better accuracy, stability, and resistance to noise compared to single decision trees, making them a preferred choice in complex classification and regression tasks [19].

3.1.1.5 Support Vector Machine (SVM)

The Support Vector Machine (SVM) is a widely used supervised learning method, particularly effective for solving classification and regression problems. SVM's strength lies in its ability to generalize to new data, making it a powerful tool for high-dimensional and complex datasets. SVM works by identifying an optimal hyperplane that separates data points of different classes, aiming to maximize the margin between the closest data points of each class, known as support vectors.

One of the critical advantages of SVM is its capacity to deliver highly accurate results, even when dealing with complex, non-linear relationships within the data. SVM achieves this by utilizing kernel functions, which transform the original feature space into higher dimensions, allowing the model to find a linear boundary in these transformed spaces. This adaptability makes SVM a robust choice for applications requiring precise classification, such as image recognition, text categorization, and medical diagnostics. However, while SVM performs well with smaller datasets, it can become computationally intensive with large datasets, requiring careful tuning to balance accuracy and efficiency[20].

3.2 Performance Assessment Metrics

The performance evaluation metrics used in this study aim to comprehensively assess the effectiveness and accuracy of machine learning models. The metrics applied in the project include training time, test time, classification accuracy (CA), recall, F1 score, area under the curve (AUC), and precision. Each metric provides detailed insights into different aspects of the model, offering a thorough understanding of its overall performance.

- **Train Time:** The duration for the model to learn from the training data.
- **Test Time:** The time taken for the model to make predictions on the test data.
- **Accuracy:** The ratio of correctly predicted instances to the total instances.
- **Recall:** The proportion of actual positive cases correctly identified.
- **F1 Score:** A balanced measure combining precision and recall.
- **Area Under the Curve (AUC):** A metric indicating the model's ability to distinguish between classes.
- **Precision:** The proportion of correctly identified positive instances predicted positively.

By measuring these metrics, the study offers a comprehensive view of the model's strengths and areas for improvement, ensuring that it is evaluated from multiple perspectives to confirm its accuracy and practical viability [14].

The confusion matrix is a tool used to evaluate the performance of a model in classification problems. It represents the relationship between actual and predicted classes, indicating how well the model classifies the instances. Defined as a two-dimensional matrix, it includes values for four distinct categories:

- **True Positive (TP):** Instances where the model correctly predicts the positive class.
- **True Negative (TN):** Instances where the model correctly predicts the negative class.
- **False Positive (FP):** Instances where the model incorrectly predicts the positive class for an actual negative instance, also known as a "Type I error."
- **False Negative (FN):** Instances where the model incorrectly predicts the opposing class for an actual positive instance, known as a "Type II error."

By analyzing these four components, the confusion matrix provides valuable insights into the model's accuracy, precision, recall, and other performance metrics, allowing for a detailed assessment of the model's classification capability.

Table 1 Confusion Matrix Example

	Prediction: Positive	Prediction: Negative
Real: Positive	True Positive	False Negative
Real: Negative	False Positive	True Negative

3.3 Cyber Security

Cybersecurity encompasses the practices, processes, and technologies to protect digital information and assets from unauthorized access, attacks, or damage. The core objectives of cybersecurity are to ensure the **confidentiality**, **integrity**, and **availability** of information, often referred to as the CIA triad. These objectives collectively safeguard sensitive data, maintain system reliability, and ensure that accessible resources are available when needed.

3.3.1 Cyber Attacks

In today's digital landscape, individuals, businesses, and governments are exposed to numerous opportunities and threats. Among these, cyberattacks stand out as one of the most significant risks, posing severe challenges to information security, business continuity, and privacy. This study focuses on some fundamental types of cyberattacks: Brute Force, HTTP DDoS, ICMP Flood, Port Scan, and Web Crawling. Each of these attacks employs different methods and serves distinct purposes, all of which threaten the security of digital systems.

3.3.1.1 Brute Force Attacks

In a brute force attack, the primary goal is to gain administrative access to the target system. With administrative privileges, an attacker can view all sensitive system settings and gain full access to the desired files. To successfully execute a brute force attack, the attacker attempts numerous combinations of usernames and passwords until gaining unauthorized access. This enables the attacker to remotely control the system, potentially resulting in significant security breaches and unauthorized access to confidential data. Brute force attacks often target systems with weak password policies, exploiting the lack of robust authentication mechanisms to compromise sensitive assets [9].

3.3.1.2 HTTP DDoS Attacks

HTTP DDoS (Distributed Denial of Service) attacks aim to overwhelm a website or service, rendering it inaccessible. These attacks are executed by flooding the target system with massive HTTP requests from multiple sources, exhausting its resources and disrupting its normal functioning. This attack can significantly impact the availability and reliability of online services, making it a critical security concern for organizations that rely on web-based applications and platforms [21].

3.3.1.3 ICMP Flood Attacks

ICMP Flood attacks aim to exhaust a target system's network bandwidth and processing resources using Internet Control Message Protocol (ICMP) packets. These attacks involve flooding the target with many ICMP requests, overwhelming the network, and slowing down or disrupting its services. This type of attack exploits ICMP as a mechanism for overload, reducing the system's ability to respond to legitimate network traffic [22].

3.3.1.4 Port Scan Attacks

Port Scan attacks identify open ports and associated services on a network or system. Attackers use port scanning tools to identify which ports are accessible, then exploit this information to uncover potential vulnerabilities. Open ports can serve as entry points for further attacks, making port scans a commonly used method for reconnaissance in cyberattacks [23].

3.3.1.5 Web Crawling Attacks

Web Crawling attacks involve using automated software tools, or bots, to collect information from websites. While web crawling is often a benign activity used by search engines to index web content, malicious actors can misuse this technique to gather sensitive information or detect exploitable content on a target site. This attack can lead to unauthorized data harvesting, causing privacy and security issues for the targeted entities [24].

4 DATA PREPROCESSING AND CLASSIFICATION

The dataset used in this study is the "Multi-Step Cyber Attack Dataset (MSCAD)" obtained from the Kaggle platform. MSCAD is a comprehensive resource for cybersecurity research, particularly in the areas of intrusion detection and attack analysis. This dataset contains six distinct labels, representing various types of cyberattacks and regular network traffic, providing a well-rounded foundation for evaluating intrusion detection systems and analyzing attack patterns. Preprocessing the data involves cleaning, transforming, and preparing it for practical model training and classification, ensuring the robustness and accuracy of the machine learning algorithms applied in this study.

4.1 Data Preprocessing

Data preprocessing refers to preparing raw data for machine learning models, ensuring it is clean, formatted, and ready for analysis. This process involves removing or correcting missing and erroneous data, transforming it into a suitable format, and enhancing its quality to improve model performance. The initial dataset consisted of 67 columns and 128,798 rows, resulting in a significant processing time due to its size. Several preprocessing steps were applied to optimize performance and reduce the dataset's size, ultimately improving computational efficiency.

As a result of these steps, a refined dataset with 92,035 rows and 57 columns was prepared. This study utilized a preprocessed dataset with machine learning techniques, including K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Neural Networks, Decision Trees, Random Forests, and Support Vector Machines (SVM). These methods were applied to the refined dataset using JupyterLab and Orange3 platforms, enabling a comparative analysis of their performance.

4.2 Classification with Preprocessed Data

Classification is a machine-learning technique that assigns data samples to specific categories or classes. Typically, classification algorithms predict which class a given data instance belongs to, learning from the dataset's features to accurately classify new data instances. In this study phase, classification algorithms were applied exclusively to the preprocessed dataset, allowing for a detailed evaluation of their effectiveness.

The performance of these models was assessed in both JupyterLab and Orange3. The dataset was divided into 70% training and 30% testing sets to facilitate the training and validation processes, enabling a robust assessment of model accuracy and generalizability.

4.2.1 Classification with Orange3

These classification processes were implemented using the Orange3 platform. Figure 2 presents the main workflow established in Orange3, showcasing the classification algorithms, the preprocessed dataset, and the evaluation metrics applied. Orange3 provided a visual and interactive

environment for implementing and assessing the classification algorithms, offering insights into the performance of each model on the preprocessed data.

Figure 2. Machine Learning Algorithms Flow Diagram

One of the classification algorithms applied was the Decision Tree classifier. On the Orange3 platform, the Decision Tree algorithm yielded the best results in terms of speed and performance, outperforming other algorithms. Its efficiency and high accuracy in classifying the preprocessed dataset make it the most suitable choice for this study's objectives. The Decision Tree's structure, which systematically divides data based on feature criteria, contributed to its superior performance, enabling quick and accurate predictions on the Orange3 platform.

In this study, the Confusion Matrix model was examined to evaluate the performance of classification algorithms. A detailed analysis was conducted on the correct and incorrect predictions for various types of attacks. As shown in Table 2, the Decision Tree correctly identifies Brute Force attacks with over 99% accuracy.

The classification methods applied to the refined dataset demonstrated varying degrees of accuracy. Brute Force attacks were identified with a high accuracy rate of 99.96%, while HTTP DDoS attacks had a correct identification rate of 95.1%. ICMP Flood attacks were less accurately identified at 74.29%, with considerable misclassifications as Normal traffic. Regular traffic was correctly classified at a rate of 99.82%, and Port Scan attacks had an accuracy rate of 98.77%. Web Crawling attacks showed the lowest accuracy, with only 26.25% correctly classified. This analysis highlights the strengths and weaknesses of the classification algorithms, providing insights for future improvements in cybersecurity systems (Table 3).

Overall, the classification algorithms demonstrated a high accuracy rate in correctly identifying attack types, providing valuable insights for enhancing the effectiveness of security systems. This analysis highlights areas

for improvement in model predictions and informs strategies for reducing misclassification in cybersecurity applications.

Table 2. Confusion Matrix Table of Labels

		Predicted						Total
		Brute Force	HTTP DDoS	ICMP Flood	Normal	Port Scan	Web Crawling	
Actual	Brute Force	265399	21	0	58	32	0	265510
	HTTP DDoS	12	1826	7	26	39	0	1910
	ICMP Flood	2	4	104	23	2	5	140
	Normal	65	7	7	85357	57	17	85510
	Port Scan	177	59	0	178	32826	0	33240
	Web Crawling	1	2	2	54	0	21	80
	Total	265656	1919	120	85696	32956	43	386390

Overall, some confusion is observed between certain attack types, indicating areas where security systems could be improved for enhanced accuracy. This analysis offers valuable insights into the strengths and weaknesses of the classification system, particularly in refining the identification of more complex attack types, such as Web Crawling.

Table 3. Percentage Confusion Matrix Table of Labels

		Predicted						Total
		Brute Force	HTTP DDoS	ICMP Flood	Normal	Port Scan	Web Crawling	
Actual	Brute Force	99,9582%	0,0079%	0,0000%	0,0218%	0,0121%	0,0000%	265510
	HTTP DDoS	0,6283%	95,6021%	0,3665%	1,3613%	2,0419%	0,0000%	1910
	ICMP Flood	1,4286%	2,8571%	74,2857%	16,4286%	1,4286%	3,5714%	140
	Normal	0,0760%	0,0082%	0,0082%	99,8211%	0,0667%	0,0199%	85510
	Port Scan	0,5325%	0,1775%	0,0000%	0,5355%	98,7545%	0,0000%	33240
	Web Crawling	1,2500%	2,5000%	2,5000%	67,5000%	0,0000%	26,2500%	80
	Total	265656	1919	120	85696	32956	43	386390

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The study evaluated the effectiveness of multiple classification algorithms, each optimized using chi-square feature selection, in detecting various types of cyberattacks in a dataset. The critical algorithms tested included Decision Trees, Random Forests, K-nearest neighbors (KNN), Neural

Networks, and Support Vector Machines (SVM). The outcomes of each model, along with its performance on different attack types, provide valuable insights into their respective strengths and limitations. Key findings of this article are:

- Decision Tree and Random Forest are the most reliable models, with Random Forest showing the best performance across chi-square optimized features.
- Further tuning or advanced architectures could enhance Neural Network and SVM models.
- Hybrid approaches and real-time testing are recommended for better detection rates and practical application insights.

The low detection rate of Web Crawling attacks (26.25%) suggests a class imbalance issue or insufficient feature discrimination. To address this, techniques such as SMOTE oversampling or class-weight tuning in algorithms could be explored.

The study concludes that, with appropriate feature selection and tuning, machine learning algorithms can significantly contribute to cybersecurity by accurately identifying various types of cyberattacks.

6 CONCLUSION

The results indicate that chi-square feature selection effectively improves model efficiency by focusing on the most relevant features, which can significantly reduce processing time without compromising accuracy. Decision Tree and Random Forest emerged as the most reliable models across various attack types, demonstrating consistent accuracy and robustness. Specifically, the Decision Tree's combination of speed and accuracy makes it highly suitable for scenarios where real-time attack detection is critical. At the same time, Random Forest continued to show the best performance across chi-square optimized features. For future work, we recommend :

- Model Optimization: Fine-tuning Neural Network and SVM models could enhance the detection of Web Crawling and ICMP Flood attacks, where they currently underperform.
- Hybrid Approaches: Combining different algorithms in a hybrid model could improve detection rates for complex attacks.
- Real-Time Testing: Implementing and testing these models in a live environment would offer insights into their practical application and robustness.

In conclusion, the study demonstrates that with the appropriate feature selection and tuning, machine learning algorithms can significantly contribute to cybersecurity by accurately identifying and classifying various cyberattacks, ultimately supporting more effective and proactive defense mechanisms.

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